

A Study on the Use of Owned Fleets in Road Transport: Benefits, Limitations, and Operational Impacts

*Um Estudo Sobre a Utilização de Frota Própria no
Transporte Rodoviário: Benefícios, Limitações e Impactos
Operacionais*

*Un Estudio sobre la Utilización de Flota Propia en el
Transporte por Carretera: Beneficios, Limitaciones e
Impactos Operativos*

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Abstract:

The management of an in-house fleet in road transport is a strategic element for enhancing companies' competitiveness, ensuring operational control, enabling route flexibility, and improving the quality of service to customers. This article aims to analyze the benefits, limitations, and operational impacts of using an in-house fleet, and to examine the balance between in-house and outsourced fleets within organizations. To achieve this, descriptive research with a qualitative approach was conducted, using the case study method through semi-structured interviews with four employees holding different positions in companies that operate both in-house fleets and third-party services. The results indicate that an in-house fleet provides greater reliability, agility, control, and flexibility. However, it entails high acquisition, maintenance, and driver-management costs, as well as challenges in training and retaining personnel. It is concluded that efficient in-house fleet management can generate a sustainable competitive advantage when integrated into a hybrid model combining in-house and outsourced fleets.

Keywords: Operational efficiency; Transport management; Logistics.

Resumo:

A gestão da frota própria no transporte rodoviário é um elemento estratégico para aumentar a competitividade das empresas, garantindo controle das operações, flexibilidade nas rotas e melhoria na qualidade do serviço prestado ao cliente. O objetivo deste artigo é analisar os benefícios, limitações e impactos operacionais da utilização da frota própria, bem como compreender o equilíbrio entre frota própria e terceirizada nas organizações. Para isso, foi realizada uma pesquisa descritiva com abordagem qualitativa, utilizando o método de estudo de caso, por meio de entrevistas semiestruturadas com quatro colaboradores de diferentes funções em empresas que operam com frotas próprias e serviços de terceiros. Os resultados indicam que a frota própria proporciona maior confiabilidade, agilidade, controle e flexibilidade, embora envolva custos elevados de aquisição, manutenção e gestão de motoristas, além de desafios na capacitação e retenção da equipe. Conclui-se que a gestão eficiente da frota própria pode gerar vantagem competitiva sustentável, quando integrada a um modelo híbrido que combina frota própria e terceirizada.

Palavras-chave: Eficiência operacional; Gestão de Transportes; Logística.

Resumen:

La gestión de la flota propia en el transporte por carretera es un elemento estratégico para aumentar la competitividad de las empresas, garantizando el control de las operaciones, la flexibilidad en las rutas y la mejora en la calidad del servicio prestado al cliente. El objetivo de este artículo es analizar los beneficios, limitaciones e impactos operativos de la utilización de la flota propia, así como comprender el equilibrio entre la flota propia y la tercerizada en las organizaciones. Para ello, se realizó una investigación descriptiva con enfoque cualitativo, utilizando el método de estudio de caso, a través de entrevistas semiestructuradas con cuatro colaboradores de diferentes funciones en empresas que operan con flotas propias y servicios de terceros. Los resultados indican que la flota propia proporciona mayor confiabilidad, agilidad, control y flexibilidad, aunque implica altos costos de adquisición, mantenimiento y gestión de conductores, además de desafíos en la capacitación y retención del equipo. Se concluye que la gestión eficiente de la flota propia puede generar una ventaja competitiva sostenible, cuando se integra a un modelo híbrido que combina flota propia y tercerizada.

Palabras clave: *Eficiencia operativa; Gestión de Transportes; Logística.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Logistics plays an essential role in the corporate landscape, serving as an optimization process that significantly contributes to both operations and strategic planning within organizations (Galkin *et al.*, 2020; Henrique, Cordeiro, & Ribeiro, 2011). In this sense, Ferreira (2018) observes that companies have increasingly moved towards the professionalization of their management, defining business strategies based on a highly competitive and globalized environment. Furthermore, according to Galkin *et al.* (2020), the intensification of competition among organizations has made interactions among various agents in the logistics sector more complex.

In this context, implementing efficient management in transportation services, driven by increased goods flow, can generate significant gains in operational efficiency. Complementarily, Chimini and Hoose (2022) emphasize that transportation is a key element of logistics, directly influencing costs and, especially, service levels for companies.

From this perspective, Besen *et al.* (2017) highlight that organizations must make a strategic decision among maintaining their own fleet, outsourcing the service, or adopting a hybrid fleet management model. It is well known that both alternatives generate costs and require careful planning. In this sense, Sacchetti (2014) adds that, although outsourcing can offer practicality and savings, owning a fleet allows for greater control over the quality, speed, and reliability of deliveries. On the other hand, according to Casagrande and Ventura (2016), transportation is one of the most outsourced sectors in organizations, possibly due to the difficulties in managing activities such as loading, unloading, and transportation, which can lead to delays and, consequently, loss of resources and customer confidence.

Along the same lines, Ballou (2011) argues that adopting a company-owned fleet can be an effective strategy to improve customer service and delivery performance. However, this decision requires significant investment, especially in vehicle acquisition, and entails risks to the long-term return on invested capital. Furthermore, Rayzer *et al.* (2017) reinforce that customer satisfaction is the main objective of companies, with deliveries being a competitive differentiator that can decisively contribute to this goal.

Additionally, Faller (2020) states that the operational area plays a crucial role in ensuring the feasibility of executing proposals under the established conditions, encompassing the management of the company's own fleet and the rigorous control of operations, with a focus on maximizing efficiency and the quality of service provided to the end customer.

Thus, the choice of this study's theme is justified by the growing relevance of logistics in the competitive performance of organizations and by the strategic importance of decision-making regarding the use of a company's own fleet. In a scenario marked by rising consumer demand for fast, safe, and personalized deliveries, understanding the operational impacts, benefits, and limitations of this choice is fundamental for companies. Furthermore, it is a decision that directly affects logistics costs, operational efficiency, and customer perception of

value.

Thus, this article aims, through descriptive research with a qualitative approach, operationalized through the case study method, to analyze, across four companies and four professionals, the benefits, limitations, and operational challenges inherent in the use of a company-owned fleet in road transport.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Fleet Management: Concepts and Strategies

Initially, transportation is fundamental to moving products along the production chain and is essential for the supply and shipment of goods within companies (Sacchetti, 2014). In this context, Chimini and Hoose (2022) indicate that transportation is considered one of the most relevant functions within logistics, not only as part of the supply chain, but also due to the availability of products in the right place and at the right time, according to customer requests, seeking competitive advantage and business profit, as argued by the same authors.

Furthermore, fleet management involves a set of integrated activities whose main objective is to ensure efficiency and continuous use of the organization's means of transport, ranging from the selection and acquisition of vehicles to the execution of preventive and corrective maintenance (Galkin et al., 2020). Fallor (2020) argues that fleet management is especially crucial for companies that depend heavily on transportation, such as those in the road transport sector. This strategic management approach goes beyond acquiring new vehicles and includes maintaining and renewing the existing fleet to optimize operational costs and ensure service reliability.

Similarly, Bowersox, Closs, and Cooper (2006) emphasize that efficient fleet management reduces logistics costs and improves customer service, directly impacting the perception of value and the company's competitive advantage. Consequently, fleet management is one of the essential pillars for ensuring efficiency and excellence in logistics services, with the fleet serving as the final link between the company and the customer, carrying not only products but also the organization's reputation, according to these authors.

Figure (2014) shows that the decision regarding fleet ownership is one of the most important transportation strategies for companies across sectors, as a well-managed fleet contributes to on-time deliveries, reduced operating costs, greater operational safety, and customer satisfaction. Complementing this, Oliva, Oliveira, and Nascimento (2024) point out that companies are continually seeking to reduce transportation costs, and the challenge for strategic management is to evaluate the best option among different fleet types.

In this context, efficient fleet management is paramount to ensuring proper vehicle functioning and achieving better results. Preventive vehicle maintenance, effective route planning, and driver training result in a more reliable service and a significantly positive experience for the recipient of the goods, according to these authors.

2.2 Advantages and Disadvantages of Using a Company Fleet for Transportation

The choice between using an in-house fleet and outsourcing in road transport is a strategic decision that directly impacts costs, operational efficiency, and the company's competitiveness (Ballou, 2011; Chimini; Hoose, 2022). Considering that the customer is the most important factor for organizations, Rayzer *et al.* (2017) emphasize that customer satisfaction is the central objective, with personalized deliveries being one of the factors that most increase it.

According to Figura (2014), a company-owned fleet, when properly managed in terms of human resources and infrastructure, can guarantee a competitive level of service, reflected in greater punctuality, fewer breakdowns, shorter response times, and greater flexibility in customer service. Furthermore, Sacchetti (2014) highlights that a company-owned fleet outperforms outsourcing in terms of delivery quality and speed, with high-quality delivery being an important competitive differentiator for customer loyalty. However, the acquisition and maintenance of a company-owned fleet involve various costs, such as transportation, preventive maintenance and vehicle replacement due to depreciation.

Quirino, Brito, and Steppan (2010) point out that financial flexibility is reduced due to investments or long-term contractual commitments for the acquisition of vehicles and equipment. In turn, Monteiro *et al.* (2018) emphasize that although the costs of owning a fleet are not always reduced, under high-frequency and high-productivity conditions, operating costs may decrease.

Additionally, the decision regarding the workforce, whether in-house or outsourced, should not be based solely on financial aspects, as operational factors, while not generating immediate financial benefits, directly impact productivity and service quality. According to Monteiro *et al.* (2018), controlling the company's own fleet enables greater productivity and quality while avoiding risks related to labor liabilities that can arise in outsourced contracts.

Table 1 – Management and Use of Own Fleet *versus* Outsourced Fleet

Aspects Evaluated	Own Fleet	Outsourced Fleet
Operational control	Greater control over quality, speed and service (Sacchetti, 2014).	Less direct control, greater dependence on third parties (Casagrande; Ventura, 2016).
Costs	High initial investments and fixed costs (Quirino; Brito; Steppan, 2014).	Lower initial investments, but variable costs can be high (Sacchetti, 2014)
Impact on customer satisfaction	It improves punctuality and quality in deliveries (Figure, 2014; Rayzer <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	It may exhibit greater variation in service quality (Besen <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
Workplace risks	Direct occupational risks (Monteiro <i>et al.</i> , 2018).	Risks of labor liabilities in outsourcing (Monteiro <i>et al.</i> , 2018).

Source: own elaboration based on cited authors.

Finally, when evaluating whether to use an owned or outsourced fleet, companies must consider not only the costs involved but also the operational impacts of this decision. As evidenced in Table 1, aligning this choice with the company's objectives, the nature of the services provided, and the level of control required over operations is essential for the success of the adopted model.

Efficient transportation management, whether through an in-house fleet or outsourced services, is a critical factor in achieving a competitive advantage, directly impacting customer satisfaction and perceived value (Bowersox, Closs, & Cooper, 2006).

3. METHOD

The methodology adopted in this study is descriptive research with a qualitative approach, conducted through a case study.

According to Turrioni and Mello (2012), descriptive research relies on previously standardized data collection techniques, among which questionnaires and observation stand out. The qualitative approach, in turn, seeks to understand the interaction between the interviewees and the context in which they are inserted, considering perceptions, opinions, and experiences that cannot be represented solely by numerical data; thus, its objective is to identify, interpret, and analyze relationships, patterns, and characteristics between variables, focusing on a deeper understanding of the phenomena studied (Turrioni; Mello, 2012).

According to Cauchick Miguel and Souza (2012), the case study is a methodological strategy that enables detailed analysis of one or more research objects, providing a deeper understanding of the subject matter.

Cauchick Miguel and Souza (2012) consist of four stages, as shown in Figure 01.

The first step is to define the conceptual basis by selecting, reading, and analyzing articles, books, and specialized websites related to the topic of this research. This review allowed for the consolidation of fundamental concepts.

Figure 01 - Methodological structure for conducting the case study research.

Source: adapted from Cauchick Miguel e Sousa (2012).

In the second stage, a semi-structured interview script was developed based on

the theoretical framework to align the questions with the research objectives. Four companies that use both their own and outsourced fleets and have modern, automated processes were selected. Four employees, working in analysis, leadership, and logistics planning positions, participated in the study.

As shown in Figure 1, the third stage consisted of data collection, carried out through semi-structured interviews, each lasting an average of 20 minutes. All interviews were recorded and subsequently transcribed to ensure accurate analysis of the information. The description of the participants is presented in Table 2.

Table 2 – List of interviewed collaborators

Function	Length of service in the position	Training	Business sector
Logistics Analyst	5 years	Logistics Technologist	Agribusiness, specializing in the production of sugar, ethanol, and electricity.
Logistics Supervisor	3 years	Technologist in Logistics and Bachelor's Degree in Business Administration	Production of various inputs used in the food industry.
Logistics Operations Manager	7 years	Logistics Technologist	Distribution and storage of manufactured products.
Logistics Assistant	3 years	Logistics Technologist	Agribusiness, supplier of inputs, machinery, implements and technical support.

Source: Author's own work.

In the fourth and final stage, a qualitative analysis of the interview data was conducted. The participants' responses were compared with the established theoretical framework, allowing for a broader understanding of the benefits and limitations of using owned and outsourced fleets in road transport. It is noteworthy that in all cases, the companies interviewed operate their own routes but also resort to third-party services, depending on demand and logistics strategy. This process enabled the establishment of comparative relationships between the results and the research objectives.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained from the interviews reveal important insights into the benefits, limitations, and operational impacts of using a company-owned fleet in road transport. According to Sacchetti (2014), companies tend to opt for their own fleet, even at higher costs, when they need to ensure speed, reliability, and specific care in cargo transportation.

The findings of this study confirm this perspective, showing that all respondents agree that using a company-owned fleet improves service levels, offers greater flexibility, enables effective operational control, and provides direct management

of the people involved in the process.

On the other hand, the Logistics Operations Manager and the Logistics Analyst highlighted significant challenges related to fleet maintenance, vehicle acquisition, and employee management, which often make it difficult to decide whether to maintain an in-house fleet or outsource the service.

4.1 Benefits of using an owned fleet

According to the Logistics Analyst, the main gains are in total operational control, enabling dynamic adjustments to delivery routes, strict adherence to deadlines, process agility, and reduced damage. This view corroborates the findings of Figura (2014) and Rayzer et al. (2017), who highlight the importance of having their own fleet as a strategic factor in ensuring delivery quality and customer satisfaction.

The Logistics Assistant and the Logistics Operations Manager add that having a company-owned fleet enables more centralized management, autonomy to define internal policies, flexibility to meet diverse customer demands, and greater process reliability. Furthermore, the Logistics Supervisor emphasizes that centralization contributes to cost savings in the medium and long term, primarily by enabling individual control of costs per vehicle and driver.

4.2 Challenges and limitations identified

Despite the benefits, respondents acknowledge that adopting a company-owned fleet involves high fixed and variable costs. Among the main critical points cited are:

- Fuel and its impact on the total cost of operation;
- Preventive and corrective maintenance of vehicles;
- Acquisition and replacement of vehicles due to depreciation;
- Investments in tracking and embedded technology;
- Driver management and training.

In addition to these factors, respondents highlighted the difficulty of hiring experienced drivers as a significant challenge, which directly impacts operational quality, meeting deadlines, and transportation safety. According to the Logistics Operations Manager, *"the shortage of qualified professionals requires continuous investment in training and team management, making it essential to develop internal strategies for driver training and retention, ensuring that the company's own fleet operates efficiently and reliably, even in the face of natural employee turnover."*

The Logistics Analyst and Supervisor emphasize that employee turnover is an additional challenge, especially for maintaining operational quality standards. According to them, continuous training and efficient team management are key factors in extending the fleet's lifespan and reducing vehicle replacement costs.

4.3 Operational and strategic impacts

Analysis of the interviews revealed that the use of a company-owned fleet

generates significant impacts on both the operational and strategic levels of the companies studied. Participants unanimously highlighted that a company-owned fleet provides greater operational control, enabling quick route adjustments, strict adherence to deadlines, and greater agility in meeting customer demands.

The Logistics Analyst emphasized that a company-owned fleet enables optimized cargo consolidation, reduced damage, and continuous improvement in service levels. The Logistics Supervisor highlighted the importance of efficient people management, continuous training, and team monitoring to maintain reliable, high-quality operations. The Logistics Operations Manager stressed that centralized fleet management ensures autonomy, flexibility in serving clients, and greater efficiency in resource allocation, thereby reinforcing perceived value and customer loyalty. The Logistics Assistant added that having a company-owned fleet enables faster, more strategic decision-making, resulting in greater competitiveness.

In this context, Table 3 summarizes the operational and strategic impacts observed by each participant, showing how the different functions complement one another to improve company performance and guide strategic decisions regarding the company's own fleet.

As the findings demonstrate, a well-managed company fleet enables the maximization of operational efficiency and the leveraging of strategic advantages, corroborating what Ballou (2011) and Sacchetti (2014) point out regarding the importance of logistics as a competitive differentiator. Furthermore, alignment among people management, fleet maintenance, and operational planning is essential to transforming a company's fleet into a strategic tool that drives customer satisfaction and sustainable competitive advantage.

Table 3 - Operational and strategic impacts of using a company-owned fleet

Interviewee - position	Operational Impacts	Strategic Impacts
Logistics Analyst	Route optimization; reduction of damage; faster delivery.	Improved service level; greater customer satisfaction.
Logistics Supervisor	Team management and maintenance	Continuous training; increased operational reliability.
Logistics Operations Manager	Centralized management; efficiency in resource allocation.	Autonomy and flexibility; customer loyalty and competitive advantage.
Logistics Assistant	Agility in operations; real-time adjustments.	Faster strategic decisions; greater competitiveness.

Source: own elaboration based on the interviews conducted.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study showed that using a company-owned fleet in road transport offers several benefits, including greater control, greater flexibility to meet customer needs, and faster deliveries. It also became evident that this helps build trust and loyalty, even generating a competitive advantage. On the other hand, it was

noted that there are significant limitations, mainly the high costs of purchasing and maintaining vehicles and the difficulty of hiring and retaining qualified drivers.

The objective of this study was to analyze the positive and negative aspects of owning a fleet, and this was achieved. The research shows that companies understand the advantages of this model, but still use outsourced transportation as a complement. This demonstrates that many organizations opt for a mixed model, seeking to balance cost, efficiency, and quality in their operations.

One limitation of the study is the small number of companies analyzed, which limits the generalizability of the results to all sectors. Future research could include more companies from different sectors and even use quantitative methods to delve deeper into the data. It would also be interesting to directly compare the impacts of owning a fleet versus outsourcing it to understand better which practices yield better results in road transport.

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